

Terpenoids. Part VIII. Synthesis of Ar. Artemisene

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The synthesis of Ar. artemisene has been accomplished by an application of the Wittig reaction with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide on 2-methyl-6-oxo-10-*p*-tolylundec-2-ene.

Ar. artemisene, a diterpene hydrocarbon, isolated from the Wormwood oil, has been given structure (I) on the basis of chemical studies and physical evidence¹.

The present studies record a synthesis of the title compound.

Ethyl 3-methyl-3-(*p*-tolyl)propionate, the starting material in this scheme, was obtained by esterification of 3-methyl-3-(*p*-tolyl)propionic acid². Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the ester (II) provided 3-methyl-3-(*p*-tolyl)propan-1-ol in 80% yield. The carbinol (III) was converted into the corresponding bromide (IV) with phosphorus tribromide in 62.5% yield. Alkylation of ethyl 7-methyl-3-oxo-6-octen-1-carboxylate with the bromide (IV) in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide afforded 2-methyl-6-oxo-7-ethoxycarbonyl-10-*p*-tolylundec-2-ene (V) in 80% yield. Hydrolysis of the β -keto-ester (V) with EtOH-KOH and subsequent decarboxylation with copper powder furnished

1. Sorm *et al.*, *Chem. Listy*, 1951, **45**, 135; *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1951, **16**, 268.

2. Mukherji *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1959, **7**, 236.

3. Cross, "Introduction to Practical I. R. Spectroscopy", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1960, pp. 58-63.

2-methyl-6-oxo-10-*p*-tolylundec-2-ene (VI) in 64% yield. The ketone was characterised through its IR absorption spectrum (*vide infra*).

Compound (V) was submitted to the Wittig reaction⁴ with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide when 2-methyl-6-methylene-10-*p*-tolylundec-2-ene (I) was obtained in 70% yield.

The synthetic hydrocarbon (I) was characterised through its IR absorption spectrum (*vide infra*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 3-Methyl-3-(p-tolyl)propionate (II).—3-Methyl-3-(*p*-tolyl)propionic acid (40.0 g.), anhydrous ethanol (60 ml), H₂SO₄ (conc. 1 ml), and dry benzene (200 ml) were refluxed (oil bath at 120°) under a constant water separator for 8 hr. After working up in the usual

4. Greenwald *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.

*Boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I. R. absorption spectra were recorded on a Beckman I. R. 5 with sodium chloride optics, using a thin liquid film.

manner, ester (II) was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. 128-30°/7mm, yield 41.2 g. (80%); n_D^{21} 1.4949. (Found: C, 75.25; H, 8.78. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$: C, 75.69; H, 8.80%).

3-Methyl-3-(p-tolyl)propan-1-ol (III).—To a well-stirred suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (3.8 g.) in anhydrous ether (150 ml) was added the ester (II) (41.2 g.) in ether (75 ml) at such a rate as to maintain the ether at a gentle reflux. After the addition, the contents were stirred and refluxed for 1 hr. and the mixture decomposed with H_2SO_4 (cold, dil.) and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed once with water, then with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution until free of acid, and finally with water. It was dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous). After removal of ether, the residual oil was distilled in vacuum to furnish (III) (26.2 g.) in 80% yield, b.p. 118-20°/ mm, n_D^{22} 1.4900. (Found: C, 80.41; H, 9.9. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{16}O$: C, 80.44; H, 9.81%).

3-Methyl-3-(p-tolyl)-n-propyl Bromide (IV).—To a cooled solution of the carbinol (III) (23.0g.) in dry benzene (30 ml) was added phosphorus tribromide (14.4 g.) dropwise under ice-cooling. The contents were allowed to stand overnight at the room temperature and then refluxed for 1 hr. On subsequent working up, the bromide (IV) was obtained at 135-40°/ 23 mm, yield 20.0 g. (62.5%), n_D^{23} 1.5265. (Found: C, 58.50; H, 6.56; Br, 31.90. $C_{11}H_{15}Br$ requires C, 58.14; H, 6.60; Br, 35.24%).

2-Methyl-6-oxo-7-ethoxycarbonyl-p-tolylundec-2-ene (V).—To a cooled solution of potassium *t*-butoxide (prepared from potassium 1.95 g. and *t*-butanol 60 ml) was added ethyl 7-methyl-3-oxo-6-octen-1-carboxylate (9.9 g.). To the resulting sodio derivative was added dropwise the bromide (IV) (11.35 g.) and the mixture was refluxed for 10 hr. on a steam bath. Excess of *t*-butanol was removed under vacuum. Water was added to the residue and the organic layer was taken up in ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the ether, the fraction distilling at 170-75°/5 mm was collected; yield 10.32 g. (60%), n_D^{22} 1.5080. (Found: C, 76.90; H, 9.20. $C_{22}H_{34}O_3$ requires C, 76.70; H, 9.36%). It developed a deep violet colour with $EtOH \cdot FeCl_3$.

2-Methyl-6-oxo-10-p-tolylundec-2-ene (VI).—The keto-ester (V) (8.0 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of KOH (7 g.), water (40 ml), and methanol (80 ml) for 10 hr. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue after cooling was acidified with HCl(dil.). The organic material was extracted with ether and dried. After evaporating the solvent the residue was mixed with copper powder (0.5 g.) and heated to 160-70° under reduced pressure when ketone (VI) came over at 132-40°/4-5 mm; yield 64%, n_D^{22} 1.5300. IR absorption spectrum showed peaks³ at 1720 cm^{-1} ($-C=O$), 815 cm^{-1} (strong), 722 cm^{-1} (1,4-benzene substitution), 1385 cm^{-1} (C.Me). (Found: C, 83.80; H, 10.22. $C_{19}H_{28}O$ requires C, 83.77; H, 10.36%).

2-Methyl-6-methylene-10-p-tolylundec-2-ene (I).—A solution of methylsulphinyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen from sodium hydride (0.12g.) and freshly distilled dimethyl sulphoxide (4 ml). The solution was cooled in a cold-water bath and stirred during addition of methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (2.08 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (7ml), whereupon the reddish colour of methylenephosphorane was produced. After stirring at the room temperature for 15 min., the ketone (VI) (0.54 g.) in THF (6 ml) was added and stirring continued for 5 hr. at 60°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured on cold water. The organic material was taken up in light petroleum and washed thrice with cold water. After removal of the solvent, the hydrocarbon (I) came over at 105°/2-4 mm; yield

0.37 g. (70%), n_D^{22} 1.5060. IR spectrum showed peaks at 1640, 1510, 1460, 1380, 1310, 1100, 1042, 1010, 980, 885, 815, and 722 cm^{-1} . Sorm and co-workers¹ report the peaks for natural hydrocarbon at 1640, 1509, 1460, 1385, 1308, 1105, 1045, 1015, 982, 888, 815, and 720 cm^{-1} . $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 271, 263, 256.5 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 2.38, 2.48 and 2.47 (lit¹ $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 271, 262.5, and 256 $\text{m}\mu$). (Found: C, 88.40 H, 11.15. Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}$: C, 88.82; H, 11.18%.)

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